

Predicting dandelion's dispersal and evaluating its invasive impact

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Abstract

Appearing worldwide, the dandelion, scientifically known as *Taraxacum officinale*, is a plant originating from Eurasia. It features a yellow flower and a 'puffball' seed head, with seeds attached to pappus, that disperse through wind aid. Their resilience to harsh environments allows them to thrive in diverse conditions, making them invasive to ecosystems. To comprehend the dandelion's dispersal and behavior, our task involves developing a model predicting its spread over 1, 2, 3, 6, and 12 months. Additionally, we aim to assess the dandelion's inciveness by computing the impact factor on its ecosystem and comparing it with two other plant species. For Task 1, an inverse Gaussian distribution model predicts dandelion distribution in a one-hectare plot over 12 months in New York State. We apply the inverse Gaussian distribution algorithm, calculating the probability of dandelion dispersal to specific locations. Considering multiple environmental factors impacting survival rates, we simulate two-dimensional random walks for dandelions using Python. We also investigate population sensitivity to input parameter changes through Python-based sensitivity analysis, quantifying each parameter's impact on the population and graphing the results. Experimental trials reveal a positive correlation between the total population and area spread of dandelions, suggesting similar environmental factor impacts both. For Task 2, a model assessing invasive species impact uses a system of differential equations. We examine factors like resource quantity, suppression degrees among invaders and natives, and poison generated by invaders. Calculating the ratio decrease in native species, economic loss, and environmental harm, the results indicate that dandelions are weaker invaders compared to other invasive species.

Keywords: Dandelion, Plant invasion, Inverse Gaussian Distribution, ODE, TOPSIS

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

Taraxacum officinale, the common dandelion, existed a long time ago in Eurasia but has now been seen in every corner of the world [1]. It is well known for its ability to spread quickly and widely and its strong adaptation to distinct types of environmental conditions.

The life cycle of a dandelion is defined by five distinct stages: plant, plant flowering, seed head developing, seed growing, and dispersing seeds by wind [1]. The seed stage starts off the cycle when dandelion seeds are dispersed by wind and spread across the field. Once they develop a deep tap root into the earth, the seeds begin to germinate and bloom into a yellow flower. In a few days, the process of seed growing is completed inside the head of the flower. Hundreds of seeds come together to resemble the shape of a 'puffball'. Each seed is attached to a floret on the flower head and bears a pappus, which acts as a parachute to facilitate wind dispersal. This cycle ends with the breeze blowing the seeds to the surrounding of the dandelion plant and repeats over.

Dandelion has an overall strong ability to survive. It can thrive in all types of extreme environmental conditions, no matter how dry and frozen the area is. Despite the dandelion's resilience to extreme climatic conditions, living in a suitable growing environment with a combination of environmental factors, including moisture, temperature, and light intensity, can help to improve the growth of dandelion. For example, they can thrive better in areas that are humid, full of sunlight and have rich soil quality. Dandelion seeds

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need a minimum soil temperature of 50 °F for germination, but if the temperature is closer to 77 °F, they can experience faster growth [2]. Thus, dandelion growth depends on the growing environment as well; optimal environmental conditions result in their thriving growth.

The dandelion plays a critical part in our human world and the balance of the ecosystem. The dandelion is edible and has a high vitamin and mineral content. People can often use it for various medicinal purposes such as a mild diuretic and incorporate their leaves and flowers into the making of wine and salad [2]. Furthermore, in nature, pollinators, especially honeybees, view them as valuable food sources [2]. Meanwhile, they compete with native plant species for food and shelter because of their fast-spreading ability and ability to tolerate different conditions, which makes them an invasive species. This portrays the complex interaction between the dandelion and its environment. While they are especially beneficial to the diet of humans and certain insects, the dandelion can pose a serious threat to the survival of the native plant species.

1.2. Problem Restatement

As the number of invasive species from external sources continues to increase, it is imperative that we intensify our efforts to study the dispersion model of a particular plant (dandelion) and establish criteria for identifying alien species, with the ultimate goal of safeguarding our environment.

We restate the problem as the following:

Question 1: We need to predict dandelion spread over 1, 2, 3, 6, and 12 months from a single adjacent puffball stage dandelion, incorporating various climatic conditions (temperate, arid, tropical) into a mathematical model.

Question 2: Analyze and formulate the impact factors of invasive species. We need to evaluate which factor best contributes to the degree of invasion. Also, we need to test our model to compute the impact factor for dandelion and apply it to the other two species usually considered invasive.

1.3. Our Approach

The topic asks us to conduct a study of dandelions including 2 different questions. The first question requires us to design a mathematical model to predict the spread of dandelions during 5 different time periods by considering various environmental conditions or factors. For this question, we develop a dispersal model with the differential equation to predict dandelions' spread according to their surrounding wind speed, wind direction, and probable location.

Next, we apply an evaluation model for question two to evaluate the impact factors for invasive species and measure the extent of the harm of each factor that inflicts on its environment.

2. Assumptions and Justifications

Assumption 1: We do not consider natural disasters and human activity that affect the spread of dandelion seed.

Justification 1: Natural disasters and human interference are uncommon, unpredictable, and irresistible. Dandelion may completely disappear in one hectare of land, which predicts diffusion models are meaningless.

Assumption 2: We assume that there are an average of 10 flowers from a single dandelion plant, an average of 175 florets on each single seed head, of which there is 1 seed on each floret. Therefore, there are on average 1750 seeds from one dandelion plant at each time.

Justification 2: According to research [3], the range of florets of each flower is 150-200, we chose a constant value of 175 because it is convenient to calculate and has less standard error.

Assumption 3: We assume the start time for our study on the single dandelion to be April.

Justification 3: Dandelion's fruiting period normally falls between April and June [4]. In other words, dandelions only begin to produce seeds and form a "puffball" head in April. This fits our dandelion scenario in the problem.

Assumption 4: We only consider the seed spread in a hectare, and dandelions not in this area will not spread seed back to the area.

Justification 4: The study only investigates the spread of dandelions within one hectare, because it is difficult to account for unknown external factors.

Assumption 5: We do not consider the factor of terrain slope.

Justification 5: The slope is a vector that contributes to the spread of dandelion, which is the same as the wind. Therefore, we only consider the wind factor since it can have the same effect on the spread and simplify the model.

Assumption 6: We assume that the dandelion species is *Taraxacum officinale*, and the 1-hectare place is located in New York City.

Justification 6: There will be more data to study as this is the most common dandelion species in the US, and there are lots of weather data about New York, which we can use to have an accurate initial value of each factor in our investigation.

Assumption 7: We only consider invasive plant species for the purpose of the study.

Justification 7: Since dandelions are plants, it is only reasonable to bring other invasive plant species into the discussion rather than invasive animal species since they have vastly different behavior and should be treated as different cases.

Assumption 8: We assume that the native species before the invasion of the invaders are at their maximum capacity population

Justification 8: Since they are the only species at this

Figure 1. Flowchart depicting the modeling processes and result of this paper

place, they will occupy all the resources for their survival, thus having the maximum population capacity at the place.

Assumption 9: We assume that the environmental damage can be measured directly by the amount of poison.

Justification 9: Since the poison released by plants can be harmful to humans and other organisms, it is safe to use the amount of poison to measure the environmental damage.

3. Variables and Terms

We have listed all the symbols and variables with their explanations in our paper in Table 1.

4. Dandelion Population Dispersal Model

4.1. Model Overview

To investigate the dispersal of dandelions within a one-hectare area over 12 months, we divided the one-hectare land into a grid of 100×100 square cells, each measuring $1m \times 1m$. This allowed us to calculate the quantity of dandelions per square meter to illustrate the distribution of dandelions.

To predict the spread of dandelions throughout 1, 2, 3, 6, and 12 months, we use the Wald analytical long-distance dispersal. The Wald analytical long-distance dispersal is a comprehensive mathematical model based on the parameters of the distinct characteristics of dandelion and its growing environment. It helps to predict an inverse Gaussian distribution of the dispersal distance of dandelions. Since we know the dandelion seeds are spread via wind dispersal, we can use a probability distribution model to estimate their dispersal direction and their dispersed proportion of an open one-acre plot of land. It is also noteworthy that the extent to which dandelion seeds are distributed across an area is affected not only by population number but also by environmental factors.

We know that each of these environmental factors contributes to the spread of dandelion seeds, and many of these factors are affected by their variables as well. Thus, we break down these main factors influencing the dandelion distribution into eight parts: settling velocity, released height, wind turbulence level, soil pH, precipitation, sunlight, temperature and wind speed.

Table 1. Definition of Each Variable

Symbol	Definition
r	The growth rate of dandelion in $1m^2$
K	The maximum capacity in $1m^2$
F	Seed settling velocity
H	Seed release height
U	Mean horizontal wind velocity between H and the ground
I	Turbulent flow parameter
ξ	Distribution scale In inverse Gaussian Distribution
λ	Distribution mean In inverse Gaussian Distribution
pH	The acidic level of soil
Pre	The amount of precipitation in 1 year
Lum	The amount of sunlight in $1m \cdot 1m$ area
t	Average temperature
I	Number of invasive species
N	Number of native species
P	Amount of toxin
μ	Natural growth rate of I
ζ	Natural growth rate of N
K_I	Carrying capacity of I
K_N	Carrying capacity of N
$\Phi(I)$	A function used to measure the effect of herbicide on I
$\Psi(P)$	A function used to measure the effect of herbicide on N based on the amount of P
α	The correlation coefficient for suppression of one species on another for resource competition
ν	The generating rate of toxin in respect to I
γ	The consumption rate of toxin in respect of P and N
τ	The natural degradation rate of toxin

4.2. Predicting a Distribution of Dandelion Population's Dispersal Distances

To make a realistic prediction of how dandelions will distribute over time, we need to first consider the features of the dandelions, wind velocity, and weather conditions. We know the dandelion's condition can be determined based on the height from which dandelion seeds are released and the terminal velocity of dandelion seeds. Using the concept of fluid mechanics [5], the Inverse Gaussian distribution predicts the dispersion of dandelions as follows:

$$f(x) = \sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{2\pi x^3}} \cdot e^{-\frac{\lambda(x-\xi)^2}{2x\xi^2}} \quad (1)$$

where x denotes the dandelion's dispersal distances. Since we need to know in which direction the entire dandelion seed distribution skews in the grid of $100m \times 100m$, we use ξ to represent the location parameter. To help visualize the area of the open land covered by dandelion seed dispersal, we use λ to represent the scale parameter for the total number of dandelion seeds being distributed.

Therefore, the probability of a dandelion seed lands in a distance between d_1 and d_2 will be

$$p(d_1, d_2) = \int_{d_2}^{d_1} \sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{2\pi x^3}} \cdot e^{-\frac{\lambda(x-\xi)^2}{2x\xi^2}} dx. \quad (2)$$

Figure 2. Diagram Depicting the Life Cycle of Dandelions.

However, each parameter does not stand alone. Research [5] suggests that it is affected by the characteristics of dandelion, especially its terminal velocity and released height, and climatic conditions, including weather and seasonal wind. Thus, there are specific types of species and environmental factors contributing to both the λ parameter and ξ parameter. We can calculate the value of λ and ξ from their corresponding equations below [5]:

$$\xi = \frac{HU}{F} \tag{3}$$

$$\lambda = \left(\frac{H}{I}\right)^2 \tag{4}$$

Here, we can see the location parameter is affected by the seed released height H , seed terminal velocity F , and horizontal wind velocity U between the ground and the released height. The scale parameter is calculated based on the released height H and the turbulent flow parameter i . Next, we make a reasonable estimation of the value of the turbulent flow parameter. To compute this value, we multiply the air density ρ and the velocity of the seed U by the characteristic diameter of the pappus L_c . Next, we divide this product by the dynamics viscosity of the fluid ξ , which in our case is air [6]:

$$I = \frac{\rho UL_c}{\xi} \tag{5}$$

According to one study about the structure of the dandelion seed, a pappus typically has a 40 mm in diameter [7]. The air will have the value of 1.8×10^{-5} Pa·s for its dynamics viscosity at 15 °C [8]. A graphic representation of the variations of the wind speed over 1 year has shown the average wind velocity to be 5.9m/s [5]. In combination, these quantitative values enable us to attain the value of 1.6061 for our turbulent flow parameter.

Finally, we establish all the numerical values for each

known and countable factor for our scale and location parameters. By plugging their related factors numerically into our parameters, we obtain the value of 9×10^{-3} for our scale parameter λ and the value of 2.997 for our location parameter ξ . Our parameters consider comprehensively the dandelion released height, its terminal velocity, wind velocity, and its turbulent flow parameter. We neglect other natural factors, such as the possibility of fire disasters, and wild storms, due to their scale of unpredictability.

4.3. The Population of Dandelion in Each Grid

According to the research [9], we conclude that the population growth of dandelions in each grid cell follows a logistic relationship as shown in the equation below:

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \left(r - \frac{rx}{K}\right)x \tag{6}$$

where x represents the population, r represents the growth constant, and K represents the maximum carrying capacity of the cell.

In this case, r and K can be considered as a function reflecting specific parameter combinations of the organism and environment.

r is achieved through the fixed dispersal rate of dandelions, meaning each dandelion generates an average of 1750 seeds during each dispersal event.

As for K , the study [10] indicates that the dandelion population in one square meter should not exceed 30 plants, and their survival probability and density are inversely proportional. Therefore, in the simulation of dispersal below, we introduced penalties for grid squares with excessive density. In this way, we model the growth of dandelions in individual grid squares following a logistic relationship, which aligns with real-world observations.

4.4. Calculating the Effect of Various Environmental Factors on Dandelion Survival

Table 2. The table shows the optimal range of tolerance for each factor influencing the dandelion’s survival rate

Variable and Factors	Range
Survival rate	[0, 1]
Sunlight intensity	[40lx, 111000lx]
Soil pH	[4, 12]
Precipitation	[90mm, 2780mm]
Air temperature	[5°C, 35°C]

Here, the so-called "variable" in the first column represents the dandelion’s survival rate, whereas the so-called

”factors” are the five variables located below the survival rate, which can result in the change of survival rate. We use the range between 0 and 1 to represent the survival rate. Any value falling in this range will determine how successful the dandelions are in surviving under various environmental factors.

4.4.1 Methods Used to Formulate the Impact of the Four Environmental Factors

Linear Regression and Log Function: Sunlight Intensity: We measure the impact of sunlight on the dandelion’s survival rate based on the concentration of sunlight in the growing environment of the dandelion. We assume the dandelion’s exposure to the amount of sunlight is equivalent to the sum of all the incoming sunlight into the environment. We take our quantitative values of sunlight concentration from different conditions, such as a cloudy day, a day without any cloud but sun, or a region with or without the shade of a tree. These inputting values create a huge gap between neighboring values of sunlight concentration within a range from 40 lx to 111000 lx [11]. Because of this wide variability in the dandelion’s exposure to sunlight, as it depends on where the environment is and under climatic conditions, we use the log function to standardize our data distribution. Thus, this helps us to easily differentiate between different levels of dandelion’s survival rate in response to changing exposure to sunlight.

Fitting Parameters: (111000, 1), (20000, 0.9), (1500, 0.7), (400, 0.5), (40, 0.2)

Quadratic Function: Soil pH: Dandelion has a wide range of tolerance to the level of pH in the soil during its growth stage, which can be as low as 4 or up to 12[5]. We derive our equation from the base quadratic function. We use the quadratic regression to best approximate the change in dandelion’s survival rate in response to the level of pH higher and lower than the optimal pH level in the soil. In our case, the dandelion has the highest survival rate in the optimal soil pH of 8. As the dandelions fall within this range of pH tolerance in soil, they will have a positive survival rate, which is between 0 and 1. However, if dandelions fall outside this range of pH tolerance, dandelions will experience a negative survival rate, meaning they have difficulty tolerating the pH and thus cannot survive. Thus, it can be logically inferred that the closer our pH level is to the optimal pH level of soil, the higher the chance of dandelion survival is.

Fitting Parameters: (4, 0), (7.1, 0.7), (8, 1), (12, 1)

Precipitation: Dandelions have a low requirement of precipitation as they can colonize and thrive in dry fields. Despite this, they do have an optimal tolerance of precipitation concentration, ranging from 90 mm and 2780 mm [12]. The use of the quadratic function can represent the best approximation of the change in the dandelion’s survival rate as the concentration of precipitation changes. In

the quadratic function, dandelion would experience a maximum survival rate when the precipitation reaches the optimal value of 850.9mm. However, the survival rate begins to decline slowly when the concentration of precipitation departs from this optimal value. In our case, as dandelions fall out of the tolerance range between 90mm and 2780 mm, they are unable to grow as quickly as they could when they are within the tolerance. More severely, a striking drop in the survival rate could be seen in the growing environment. Fitting Parameters: (90, 0), (304.8, 0.8), (577, 0.9), (850.9, 1), (1124, 0.9), (1397, 0.8), (2780, 0)

Air Temperature:

The germination of dandelion is influenced by air temperature in a limited range from 5 °C to 35 °C [1], and warmer air temperatures tend to promote faster and more successful germination. However, extreme temperatures, whether too hot or too cold, can inhibit or delay the germination process. The using of the quadratic function allows us to approximate how the survival rate of dandelions changes in response to air temperatures above and below the optimal temperature. In our study, we found that dandelions have the highest survival rate when the air temperature is at an optimal 25°C. As the air temperature varies within the range of 5 to 35 °C [13], the survival rate is expected to decrease gradually, forming a parabolic relationship. Therefore, we can infer that the closer the air temperature is to the optimal temperature, the greater the chances of dandelion survival.

Fitting Parameters: (5, 0), (25, 1), (35, 0)

Above all, we can summarize the probability of survival of dandelion seed:

$$P_{survive} = P_{Lum} \cdot P_{pH} \cdot P_{Pre} \cdot P_t \quad (7)$$

4.5. The Spread of Dandelion

Assume that there is a dandelion in point (x_0, y_0) , it will spread dandelion seed to point (x, y) . The Euclid distance can represent as followed:

$$d = \sqrt{(x_0 - x)^2 + (y_0 - y)^2} \quad (8)$$

After knowing the distance, we can calculate the amount of seeds land in point (x, y) .

$$P_{land(x,y)} = \int_{d+0.5}^{d-0.5} \sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{2\pi x^3}} \cdot e^{-\frac{\lambda(x-\xi)^2}{2x\xi^2}} dx \cdot P_{survive} \quad (9)$$

Above all, when dandelions spread each time, We use a **Two-Dimensional Random Walk** to calculate the landing points of new dandelions. The following are our steps:

- First, since one mature dandelion can produce an average of 1750 seeds, we randomly generated 1750 distances following an inverse Gaussian distribution to determine the spread distance for each seed.

Table 3. Table shows the measurable impact of each natural factor on the survival rate in the forms of linear and quadratic regressions. In these regression equations, y denotes the survival rate, and x denotes its corresponding factors, which are sunlight intensity, soil pH, air temperature, and precipitation.

Factors	Symbol	Regression equations	Sources
Sunlight Intensity	p_{Lum}	$y = 0.23189 \log(Lum) - 0.115747$	[11]
Soil pH	p_{pH}	$y = -0.0625pH^2 + pH - 3$	[14]
Precipitation	p_{pre}	$y = -5.53784 \cdot 10^{-7}Pre^2 + 0.00159Pre - 0.13831$	[12]
temperature	p_t	$y = -0.00444t^2 + 0.17778t - 0.77778$	[13]

- Based on the wind direction, we randomly determined the angle of dispersion for each seed (within a 45-degree range above and below the wind direction).
- Considering the survival rate, we randomly selected seeds that survived.

In the simulation, we use the method above, and **other environment factors** are as follows:

- The selected land is located near New York, and prevailing winds are mostly from the southwest or northwest [15]. Most seeds are expected to drift towards the upper right or lower right corners of the land.
- based on weather data [16], we obtained information on precipitation and average sunlight exposure in the New York area.
- The soil pH value for the New York region was obtained from the U.S. Department of Agriculture [17] and used as a parameter for calculating seed survival rates.

Figure 3 are the results of a two-dimensional random walk simulation based on the probabilities calculated using the inverse Gaussian distribution: The dandelion spread simulation shows the progression of dandelion seed dispersal over several months. In the first month, the seeds spread outward from the parent dandelion, creating a ring-shaped distribution within a limited radius. By the second month, matured dandelions in each position from the previous month randomly spread their seeds, resulting in a slightly more clustered distribution. In the third month, a relatively dense distribution of seeds is formed based on the previous spreading pattern. By the sixth month, the area covered by dandelion seeds nearly doubles and spreads even farther away from the center. Finally, in the twelfth month, an extremely dense distribution of dandelion seeds is observed, almost twice the size of the distribution in the sixth month.

4.6. Effects of Various Climatic Conditions on Dandelion Growth.

The goal of the sensitivity analysis is to understand how changes in certain input parameters affect the population growth and spread of dandelions over time. The analysis aims to evaluate the impact of variations in environmental factors, such as wind, sunlight, precipitation, and pH, as well as the slope direction and slope value on the spread and growth of dandelion populations. By analyzing the sensitivity of population growth and spread to changes in input parameters, we can dive deeper and understand better the critical factors influencing dandelion populations and their spatial distribution. Our analysis can be used as a useful reference for our future land management and biodiversity conservation techniques.

4.6.1 The Range and Mean Value of variable

Table 4. The Mean Value and the Range of Each Variable

Symbol	Average	min	max	source
F	0.3m/s	0.1	1	[18]
H	0.1524m	0.05	0.45	[19]
U	5.9m/s	1	10	[5]
i	0.6061	0.5	1.5	[20]
pH	8.0	4	12	[13]
Pre	850.9	90	2780	[13]
Lum	10000	40	111000	[3]
t	25	5	35	[13]

Figure 3. The results of a two-dimensional random walk simulation based on the probabilities calculated using the inverse Gaussian distribution

4.6.2 Sensitivity Analysis Result

The following eight different graphs show the changes in the dandelion population under the influence of different environmental factors, including the settling rate of the seed (F), the released height of dandelion seeds (H), the wind speed (U), the wind turbulence level (i), the pH level of soil, the precipitation, the amount of light available for dandelions, and the air temperature.

For each graph, the y-axis represents the course of time (in months), the z-axis represents the total population, and the x-axis represents the specific values for different environmental factors and ranges. Figure 5, the increasing settling velocity is shown to be indirectly proportional to the population of dandelion seeds, because seeds with higher settling velocity are more likely to fall in closer proximity to the parent plant. This will result in higher competition for resources among seedlings in those areas and thus higher deaths of dandelions.

Figure 6, on the other hand, a higher released height of seeds can lead to an increasing population, because how high the dandelion seeds are released determines how far they can travel from their parent dandelion. This enables seeds to catch stronger air currents, potentially resulting in longer dispersal distances. The total population will thus increase as it increases the chances of colonization in new areas and reduces competition for resources with nearby par-

ent plants. Figure 7, an increase in turbulence level drastically decreases the population. A growing turbulence level will increase the air resistance against the spread of dandelion seeds through airflow, preventing seeds from going further and resulting in competition for resources near the parent plant.

Figure 8, the population of seeds will increase as the pH level of the soil gets closer to the optimal level for dandelion germination since different plant species have specific pH requirements for optimal germination. If the soil pH deviates from the preferred range, it can inhibit or delay germination, reducing the success rate of germination and potentially limiting the population size. Figure 9, the population of dandelions is closer to its maximum on its way to optimal precipitation, because seeds require moisture to begin their germination process, and a sufficient amount of precipitation offers seeds enough water for absorption, which facilitates their growth. Insufficient precipitation can result in reduced germination rates and hinder seedling establishment, leading to lower population sizes.

Figure 10 demonstrates sunlight has very little impact on the population of dandelions. Sunlight serves as the primary source of energy for photosynthesis, which means there is no repulsion between sunlight and dandelions. When the dandelion receives the right amount of sunlight necessary for its growth, an excessive amount of sunlight won't result in an evident increase in the population trend. Figure 11, the

Figure 5. The Impact of F on the Population

Figure 6. The Impact of H on the Population

population of dandelion gets closer to its maximum as the temperature moves to its optimal level. This is because different plant species have specific temperature requirements for germination, and any extreme temperature can inhibit or delay germination, reducing germination success rates and potentially limiting population size. As for Figure 12, a small increase in wind speed can largely increase the population of dandelions, because wind can carry lightweight seeds over long distances, allowing them to colonize new areas and contribute to population expansion.

4.6.3 Analysis of the Graphs

Aside from analyzing the impact of each variable on the population, we need to address to what extent each of these variables makes a contribution to the population trend in each month.

Since the beginning of the year is when the dandelion seeds are dispersing by wind, we are unable to make a conclusive statement about which factor has the most significant impact on the population. Projecting to the next two months, we begin to see almost all the environmental factors (except for the wind turbulence level and the wind speed) cast effect on the dandelion population growth, but we can hardly tell which variable is the most significant.

From month 6 onwards, we can see a clear distinction between each factor in terms of their effect on the dandelion population. Based on our judgment on the second half of the graphs for each factor, we can conclude the wind speed has the greatest impact on the population trend because when the wind speed reaches 10 m/s, we can see there is an exponential population growth of dandelions takes place, which

rises rapidly approximately 1000 to over 3000 in the last two months.

The factors H , F , and Lum have demonstrated a linear relation with the population. They cause certain positive changes to the dandelion population, but they aren't as significant as the one we see in the graph of wind speed, illustrated by the slower growth rate of linear relation than the exponential function. In addition, factors related to the survival rate of the dandelion, such as pH and Pre , have a significant population change when it reaches an extreme value and a relatively small impact when it is close to the optimal value.

4.7. Relationship Between Total Population and Spread Area

To explore the relation between total population and spread area in 1 to 12-month spreading of dandelion, we changed different factors and ran 100 experimental trials to determine the ratio between total population and spread area as illustrated in the following: From this graph, we can conclude that there is a positive relationship between the total population and the spread area of dandelions. The vertical axis shows the density of the dandelions in each month, in which there are an average of 2.5 dandelions per spread grid, 1-meter square in 1 hectare, in the first 2 months. This number increase to 5 in month 3, increase to 10 in month 7 and 8 and finally reach 15 in month 10. After month 10, it is winter and the weather is getting cold, so the dandelion stops spreading and the density will remain constant.

Figure 7. The Impact of i on the Population

Figure 9. The Impact of Pre on the Population

Figure 8. The Impact of pH on Population

Figure 10. The Impact of Lum on the Population

4.8. Conclusion of Inverse Gaussian Distribution and Sensitivity Analysis

We use the inverse Gaussian distribution model based on the probability from one location to the next location in an open one-hectare plot of land to predict the distribution of dandelions over 1 month, 2 months, 3 months, 6 months, and 12 months. This model, however, cannot be used to solve our problem purely since it does not incorporate the climatic conditions and the physical condition of dandelions into consideration. To ensure the reliability of our model, we use sensitivity analysis to evaluate the impact of various environmental factors, including the seed’s settling velocity, released height, wind velocity, soil pH, and sunlight inten-

sity, on the dandelion’s survival rate to determine the total population of dandelions, thus helping us to make a reasonable judgment about the spread area of dandelions.

5. Invasion Impact Factor Evaluation Model

5.1. Model Overview

To determine the impact factor for our invasive plant species, we combined two types of models: a competition model and an evaluation model.

We use an invasive species-native species competition model to describe the damage cast by dandelion and other

Figure 11. The Impact of t on the Population

Figure 12. The Impact of U on the Population

Figure 12. The ratio of Total Population and Spread Area.

plant invasive species on the ecosystem equilibrium, the state of health of the invaded terrain, and the economic profitability of farmers and agriculture-based businesses. Afterward, we feed those data into an evaluation model to assess the surviving performance of different invasive plants in diverse environments. This allows us to measure quantitatively the degree of impact various invasive species have had on the environment.

5.2. Competition Model between Invasive Species and Native Species

In general, invasive plant species tend to compete with native plant species for resources when they intrude on the native territory. However, different types of invasive plant species have various characteristics and thus we cannot gen-

eralize them. Common dandelions, for instance, are edible, which makes them non-toxic. But there are cases where certain plant species are poisonous. *Crotalaria* spp., a specific plant group, accumulates a toxin of what is scientifically known as pyrrolizidine alkaloids, which can cause liver disease and will kill the animal if it is severe enough [21]. We will also consider other plant characteristics of the invasive and native, including their natural growth rate and carrying capacity, to make a comprehensive analysis of the effect of invasiveness.

We analyze the population dynamics of two competing plant species, one of them is an invasive species with or without phytotoxin, which is highly harmful to the growth of plants. This competition setting can be best described by ordinary differential equations since derivatives can be used to represent the change of rate of species.

We would also incorporate other environmental parameters to make our model more generalized. Thus, we propose a system of three partial differential equations to study the invasion mediated by the invasive plant species and how such an invasion can affect the number of native plant species when resource competition and toxins are integrated into our model. Below are the differential representations of this interaction between the invasive species with or without

phytotoxin and the native species [22]:

$$\frac{\partial I}{\partial t} = \mu I \left(1 - \frac{I + \alpha_1 N}{K_I} \right) - \Phi(I) \tag{10}$$

$$\frac{\partial N}{\partial t} = \zeta N \left(1 - \frac{N + \alpha_2 I}{K_N} \right) - N\Psi(P) \tag{11}$$

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial t} = \nu I - \gamma PN - \tau P \tag{12}$$

$$\tag{13}$$

In the differential equations above, μ represents the growth constant of the invading species and ξ represents the growth constant of the native species. α_1 and α_2 represent the suppression constant of one species on another for the contention of natural resources. The higher α of one species to another is, the more likely it will out-compete the latter. K represents the carrying capacity of our invasive and native species. We conceptualize the idea of limiting reagent into our mathematical derived equation of K , which is shown as the following:

$$K = \min \left(\frac{W}{W_{req}}, \frac{E}{E_{req}} \right) \tag{14}$$

where W denotes the total amount of water resource needed to support the entire species population in the area, W_{req} denotes the required amount of water to support the survival need of an individual species.

The division of W and W_{req} represent the total species population supported by the sum of water resources. E represents the sunlight energy and has an identical meaning to math symbols as W . Whichever resources, either water or sunlight energy, get consumed first will limit the species population supported by the area.

By comparing the population supported by the water with the one supported by the sunlight energy, we use the min function to help us select the smaller population number, which is our carrying capacity of the plant species. We can do our calculation of carrying capacity separately for both our invasive plant species and native plant species and thus we will receive our values of carrying capacity.

Furthermore, the function $\Phi(X)$ represents the effect of herbicide on the species. This can be shown in the Equation 15 where I represents the population of the invading species, θ represents the threshold value of the invading species population for the herbicide to be put in use (farmers tend to use herbicides once they notice the trend of invasion by observing the number of them), and $\sigma(I)$ represents the engagement constant for herbicide on the invading species.

$$\Phi(I) = \begin{cases} 0 & I \leq \theta \\ \sigma I & I > \theta \end{cases} \tag{15}$$

Furthermore, $\Psi(P)$ here represents the poison elimination function, which outputs the number of native species being killed. This is shown in the Equation 16 where θ here

represents the threshold at which the poison starts to affect the native species and β and η control the efficiency of the poison on the native plants.

$$\Psi(P) = \begin{cases} 0 & P \leq \theta \\ \beta \frac{P - \theta}{\eta + (P - \theta)} & P > \theta \end{cases} \tag{16}$$

5.3. Data Generation

For this study, along with dandelions, we also incorporated two more invasive species: Kudzu and Giant Hogweed. For each of them (including dandelions), we tested their impact on the population of different native species, including ryegrass (grass), coast redwood (tree), and alfalfa, under different environments. Kudzu, not only kills native species by blocking the sunlight like dandelion but it also has significant damage to the trees by inserting its roots into the tree and sucking their nutrient, and slowly killing them all. The giant hogweed kills the native species not only by blocking the sunlight but also by releasing lethal phytotoxin. Also, for different ecosystems, there are different amounts of initial equilibrium for different native species populations since they all have different amounts of resources and different species require different amounts of each type of resource. We assume that the initial total population of grass, tree, and alfalfa is 100000, 1000, and 12500, and the number of invasive species for grass, tree, and alfalfa is 100, 1, and 6, which are consistent for all three invasive species.

Also, for each incisive species, we tested their impact on three different native species: grasses, trees, and alfalfa. Among them, grasses are the most vulnerable to invasive species (meaning that one invading individual can kill a lot of grass) but have the fastest growing rate and the lowest economic value, trees have the highest economic value per individual and the strongest relative resistance toward invasive species yet the slowest growth rate among all individuals. Alfalfas are a moderate example of grasses and trees as they have decent resistance, growth rate, and economic values compared to the other two. This will generate 9 cases in total, which is shown in the Figure 13. In Figure 13, the green line represents the native species, the blue line represents the invasive species, and the red line represents the amount of poison. We can see the population decrease of each native species after 24 months of development.

Comparing the Invasive Species, we can see that **Kudzu** have the greatest affect on invading trees and grass, and **Giant Hogweed** have the greatest effect on invading Alfafa due to its toxic feature.

Comparing the Native Species, we can see that the smallest amount of change is trees and the largest is the Alfafa, this shows that trees is have strong ability to resist invasive species but the economic plantation such as Alfafa can not survive with in the competition with invasive species. Grass

Figure 13. The result population and poison of all 9 cases

hardly survive when it is competing with strong invasive species like Kudzu, but the amount of grass only decrease a half when it is competing against Dandelion and Giant Hogweed.

5.4. Evaluation Model

In the Table 5, we derive the number decrease of native species in ratio from the 9 Figure 13. Then, we calculate the economic cost based on the product of the ratio of the number decrease in native species population and the initial value of each native species, including ryegrass (\$0), coast redwood (\$1262.5) [23], and alfalfa (around \$2) [24]. For

environmental harm, we measure the toxin level based on the toxicity of different invasive plants. Because when the indicator is larger, the plant can do more damage to the environment, we use the following formula for normalization and get the indicator after normalization:

$$x_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij} - x_{min}}{x_{max} - x_{min}} \tag{17}$$

Calculate D+ and D-: For each case, compute the Eu-

Table 5. evaluation indicator

Case	Number decrease (ratio)	Economic cost	Environmental harm
Dandelion Vs. Grass	0.458	0	0
Dandelion Vs. Tree	0	0	0
Dandelion Vs. Alfalfa	0.915	22886	0
Kudzu vs. Grass	0.964	0	0
Kudzu Vs. Tree	0.675	852188	0
Kudzu Vs. Alfalfa	0.957	23920	0
Giant Hogweed Vs. Grass	0.574	0	9873
Giant Hogweed Vs. Tree	0.117	15150	80
Giant Hogweed Vs. Alfalfa	0.984	24618	455

Table 6. evaluation indicator after normalized

Comparison	Number decrease (ratio) 1	Economic cost 2	Environment harm
Dandelion Vs. Grass	0.4654	0	0
Dandelion Vs. Tree	0	0	0
Dandelion Vs. Alfalfa	0.9300	0.020	0
Kudzu Vs. Grass	0.9797	0	0
Kudzu Vs. Tree	0.6860	1	0
Kudzu Vs. Alfalfa	0.9726	0.0280	0
Giant Hogweed Vs. Grass	0.5833	0	1
Giant Hogweed Vs. Tree	0.1189	0.0326	0.0813
Giant Hogweed Vs. Alfalfa	1	0.02889	0.4624

clidean distance to the Ideal and Negative-Ideal solutions.

$$D_i^+ = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (X_{ij} - Z_j^+)^2} \tag{18}$$

$$D_i^- = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (X_{ij} - Z_j^-)^2} \tag{19}$$

Here, X_{ij} represents the normalized value for the i -th alternative and j -th criterion, Z_j^+ is the Ideal solution for the j -th criterion, and Z_j^- is the Negative-Ideal solution for the j -th criterion. **Calculate C:** For each case, compute the

Table 7. the Euclidean distance to the Ideal and Negative-Ideal solutions.

Comparison	D_i^+	D_i^-
Dandelion Vs. Grass	0.6582	0.4654
Dandelion Vs. Tree	0	0
Dandelion Vs. Alfalfa	1.3012	0.0335
Kudzu Vs. Grass	1.3855	0.9797
Kudzu Vs. Tree	1.0481	1.2127
Kudzu Vs. Alfalfa	1.3558	0.9730
Giant Hogweed Vs. Grass	1.0833	1.1577
Giant Hogweed Vs. Tree	0.03206	0.2457
Giant Hogweed Vs. Alfalfa	1.1100	1.1063

C value by the following formula:

$$C_i = \frac{D_i^-}{D_i^- + D_i^+} \tag{20}$$

As shown in the table above, we can infer the following:

Table 8. The final evaluation indicator

Comparison	C_i	Rank
Dandelion Vs. Grass	0.4142	6
Dandelion Vs. Tree	0	9
Dandelion Vs. Alfalfa	0.0251	8
Kudzu Vs. Grass	0.4142	6
Kudzu Vs. Tree	0.5364	1
Kudzu Vs. Alfalfa	0.4178	5
Giant Hogweed Vs. Grass	0.5166	2
Giant Hogweed Vs. Tree	0.4357	4
Giant Hogweed Vs. Alfalfa	0.4893	3

- **Kudzu** seems to be the most concerning plant overall, ranking 1st when compared to both Grass and Alfalfa. This could indicate higher negative impacts on native species, economic losses, or both.
- In the real world, **Kudzu** is notorious for its ability to overtake landscapes, covering trees, buildings, and structures. This rapid growth can lead to substantial economic losses by damaging infrastructure and reducing the productivity of agricultural lands. Also, it is on the invasive species list in the National Invasive Species Information Center [25]
- **Giant Hogweed** is consistently ranked higher than Dandelion and Kudzu, suggesting that it might pose significant threats in terms of native species decrease, economic losses, and the potential presence of poison.

- In real words, **Giant Hogweed** due to its ability to out-compete and displace native vegetation. Additionally, the potential health risks associated with its toxic sap contribute to its overall negative impact, it is considered a strong invasive species and it is on the invasive species list in the National Invasive Species Information Center [26].
- **Dandelion** consistently ranks lower in comparison to the other two plants, and the final evaluation indicator it is typically not invasive, especially when dandelion compete with trees and Alfafa.

Therefore, we judge that the Kudzu and Giant Hogweed is an invasive species, but dandelion should not be recognize as an invasive species.

5.5. Sensitivity Analysis

5.5.1 Model Overview

To evaluate which of these variables would have the greatest effect on the native species, we input the population model into Python. We set a range for the coefficients and parameters that affect the each of variables. We used both graphical and the Sobol method to analyze the contribution of each variable to the output of the model. The graphs created for the graphical analysis below demonstrate the amount of change in the native species population for each factor when setting to different values.

5.5.2 Sensitivity of Each Variable

Next, to gather quantitative values for the sensitivity of each variable, we utilize the Sobol method [27] to find the impact of each variable on the change of the function. The Sobol method is based on the variance of the output of the model. It decomposes the variance of the output into fractions which can be attributed to inputs or sets of inputs. These fractions can be used to determine different sensitivity indexes for different variables.

For our experiment, we calculate the total-effect sensitivity index (ST) for each of our variables. When the value of ST for a certain variable is close to 1, this means that a slight change in that variable will cause a huge change in the output of the model, thus indicating a greater sensitivity. In this case, we ignored W_{req} and E_{req} as they are predetermined based on the data gathered and do not have a huge impact on the results.

After using the Sobol Method to analyze our model, we obtained the following result: As shown in the Figure 14, the variable with the greatest ST value is *sunlight_en* (E) with a value of 0.50. The variable with the second greatest ST value is *soil_nu* (W) with a value of 0.45 followed by a_2 and a_1 as the variable with the third and fourth greatest ST values. However, the ST values of the rest of the variables

Figure 14. The graph showing ST of each variable

are significantly less than the previous four variables, all of which are close to zero. This indicates these other variables have contributed little to the result of the model.

5.5.3 Theoretical Support

The results from the graph can be explained using common sense. As nutrients and sunlight energy increase, there will be more available resources for all species, thus it will impact the number of species significantly so that more individuals (both invaders and native species) will survive. Therefore, even a small change in the amount of resources in the ecosystem will cause a huge change in the population of the invaders and the native species.

In addition, the suppression constant α also has a huge impact on the population of the invaders and the native species. When the constant of suppression on the native increases (meaning that the invaders can gain more resources on the native species), the number of native species at equilibrium will decrease significantly as a result of that, and vice versa. Therefore, the suppression constant also has a great impact on the number of invaders and native species.

5.6. Conclusion of Invasion Impact Factor Evaluation Model

We used the ODE model to calculate the impact of each invasive species on the reduction of native species, economic losses, and the quantity of toxin production. After considering these factors, we computed the “impact factor” of the invasive species to determine whether it qualifies as an invasive plant. In our TOPSIS model, accurately

assessed whether a species should be considered invasive in different scenarios (farm, forest, lawn), and our results aligned with the actual situations.

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, we develop a model that predicts the spread of dandelions based on the inverse Gaussian distribution incorporated with other whether factors including wind direction and pH to yield an accurate result. The simulation successfully represent our dispersal model that describe the reality spread of dandelion in 1 hectare and a time period of 12 months.

We analyze the factor that have the greatest influence on the growth of population is U , horizontal wind velocity, which is match with the facts.

We then come up with an evaluation model that generates the impact factor of different invading species under different circumstances based on their decrease in native population, economic damage, and environmental harm. In order to calculate these indicators, we use an Ordinary Differential Equation to calculate the relation among the amount of native species, the amount of invasive species, and the amount of poison. This helps us to judge an species whether or not it should be recognize as an invasive species. We then perform a solid sensitivity analysis that outlines the important factors that will generate a significant change in result. These models will help with the work of predicting the spread of dandelions and evaluating their impact in an established ecosystem.

7. Strengths and Weaknesses

7.1. Strengths

- **Clear problem statement:** The forecast of dandelion proliferation and the assessment of its effects on the ecosystem are the explicit problems that the material addresses.
- **Comprehensive approach:** The content outlines two different models being developed to address the problem, including a dispersal model using inverse Gaussian distribution for dandelion distribution prediction and an evaluation model with differential equations to analyze the competition between invasive and native species.
- **Consideration of environmental factors:** The content mentions the consideration of multiple environmental factors, such as temperature, moisture, and light intensity, when determining the dandelion's survival rate and population growth.
- **Sensitivity analysis:** The content describes the use of sensitivity analysis to quantify the impact of input pa-

rameters on population growth and dispersal, showing a thorough evaluation of the model's performance.

- **Integration of different methodologies:** The content mentions the use of algorithms, statistical methods (TOPSIS), and differential equations to develop and analyze the models, indicating a multidisciplinary approach.

7.2. Weaknesses

- **Model simplification:** We simplified the two-dimensional random walk model due to the complexity of its underlying principles and the lack of significant factors affecting dandelion dispersal within a short period of time.
- **Fluctuations in dandelion population:** We cannot avoid variations in the simulated dandelion population under constant parameter settings. This is because the actual survival rate can only approach the set value indefinitely, subsequently affecting the spread. However, this corresponds to the presence of other minor factors in reality that influence dandelion dispersal.
- **Limitation on considering invasive animal species:** For this study, we only consider invasive plant species. However, there are still many invasive animal species that will harm the native species mentioned in the study. Therefore, our model might not work for those types of species.

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